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GHGA Archive Model: Enabling FAIR and Secure Access to Genomic Data through Advanced Metadata Management

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Abstract

The Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) has estimated that over sixty million patients would have their genome sequenced by the end of 2025 [1]. As the volume and complexity of genomic datasets continue to grow, ensuring efficient data storage, retrieval, and controlled access remains a critical challenge. The German Human Genome-Phenome Archive (GHGA) is an omics data infrastructure designed to enable secure, scalable, and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) access to human genomic and associated phenotypic data [2]. To address these challenges, we implemented a semantic metadata framework that ensures compliance with global genomic data-sharing initiatives such as the Federated European Genome Archive and minimum information standards such as MINSEQE (Minimum Information about a high-throughput sequencing experiment) [3] and minSCe (Minimum information about a single-cell experiment) [4].

Based on functionality, the GHGA metadata model is categorized into two categories namely research metadata and administrative metadata. Through this, the model ensures that both the genomic and phenotypic data are structured efficiently for both scientific discovery and operational management while maintaining compliance with legal, ethical, and security standards.

The Research metadata describes the scientific content of datasets and enables researchers to locate, interpret, and utilize genomic data effectively. Structurally, the model resembles a bottom-up experimental approach, where submitters first define metadata to describe the scientific content of datasets, enabling researchers to utilize genomic data effectively. This includes information that characterizes phenotypic traits associated with the individual under

study (Individual), biological samples (Sample), sequencing methodologies (Experiment Method) and data processing pipelines (Analysis Method). Furthermore, the metadata model controls submitted data through three different classes, namely Research Data File, Process Data File, and Supporting File. A Research Data File holds the raw data that is the basis for further processing and analyses, which will result in a Process Data File. A Supporting File can be submitted for Experiment Method, Analysis Method and the Individual and may contain additional (un-) structured details, such as protocols or phenopackets.

The Administrative metadata manages the operational aspects that govern data access. Submitters define datasets based on the research metadata, each of which is regulated by a Data Access Policy and governed by a Data Access Committee. Finally, Datasets are linked to a Study, which is defined as the enclosed data context for data submitted to and archived in GHGA. The integration of these metadata layers allows GHGA to provide reducing manual efforts for researchers while maintaining transparency and accountability in genomic data handling.

A critical aspect of the metadata model is its standardized annotation framework, which ensures that genomic and phenotypic data are consistently described, indexed, and linked for efficient retrieval and interpretation. The GHGA metadata schema is built using the LinkML framework [5] integrating widely accepted ontologies and data models such as Data Use Ontology [6], Human Phenotype Ontology [7], or ICD-10 [8]. Apart from this, GHGA also maintains internally curated controlled vocabularies for fields that cannot be standardized using existing ontologies.

To summarize, the GHGA metadata model lays the foundation for a scalable, secure, and FAIR-compliant ecosystem for omics data with rich metadata annotation, automated access controls, and ontology-driven search capabilities. GHGA streamlines data discovery and sharing while upholding privacy, regulatory, and ethical standards.

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Competing interests

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- [8] ICD-10 website - <https://www.icd-code.de/>